

Fabrication of Conductive and Transparent Single Walled Carbon Nano Tube Film with PEDOT

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1. General Introduction

Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) is one of the most favorable materials that are used in research area such as transparent electrode. They are highly conductive with providing high transparency. Now days most of the display panels are fabricated by use of ITO, however it shows some weakness. Lack of resources, high expense to pattern on the desired substrate, and mostly poor flexibility are limiting its applications. ITO film tends to crack due to its nature of brittleness when film is bent. Many researchers are trying to find alternative materials to replace them. Numerous approaches have been done by engineers to make transparent and conductive layers to replace ITO film. Alternatively, Single Walled Carbon Nano Tube (SWCNT) has been used to fabricate conductive and transparent layers in now days [1]. SWCNT show some interesting features. They have broad range of conductivity ($10-10^7 \Omega/\text{cm}^2$), excellent transparency, good adhesion, good chemical resistance, and good flexibility [1]. Although SWCNT does present good conductivity and transparency, some limitations still present. To commercialize the SWCNT film, high value of transparency and conductivity must be achieved. However, SWCNT film has critical problem. As conductivity increases, transparency decreases. The main reason is the accumulation of SWCNT so that the transparency decreases [2]. To overcome this problem, conductive polymers were applied on to the SWCNT film [3]. In the experiment performed, simple spraying method has been used to deposit SWCNT on the Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) film. Additionally, polythiophene has been applied on to the substrate by electro polymerization to improve conductivity without sacrificing any transparency. Polythiophene has been coated on the SWCNT film by unique and simple method.

2. Experimental

2.1 Fabrication of SWCNT film

SWCNT was purchased from Nano Solution Ltd, Air Compressor was purchased from Anset IWATA Co., Ltd. Specific amount of SWCNT in a solution was sprayed multiple times to gain good transparency and conductive layer on the PET film. SWCNT solution was prepared by first filling in SWCNT into the microtubes and centrifuging for certain amount of time to separate SWCNT and surfactant. Leaving very small amount of surfactant, most of the surfactant solutions were taken away by use of pipette to avoid surfactant accumulation on the SWCNT after spraying. Removed quantity of surfactant was refilled with distilled water to generate homogeneous formation of SWCNT on the pet film.

2.1 Electropolymerization of EDOT

3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene(EDOT), 4-Dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid(DBSA) has been bought from Aldrich, and used as received. EDOT-DBSA complex was prepared by mixing distilled water and DBSA in stoichiometric ratio for one hour. EDOT was then added to the solution for 3 to 5 hour to form EDOT-DBSA complex. After completing the mixing procedure, the solution was poured into the electropolymerization stage to run the reaction. 1.5V was applied for short period of time and colorless polymers were synthesized on the SWCNT film. SWCNT-Polythiophene composite was then washed with distilled water and isoprophyl alcohol to remove any remaining surfactant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. SWCNT film fabrication

In the SEM image (Fig. 1) of the SWCNT deposited on the PET film, it can be clearly seen that SWCNT bundles are lying on the PET film. They are positioned at random location. In the experiment, many variables were changed such as adjusting the height between substrate and the air compressor nozzle, the power of air compressor, and amount of SWCNT solution per each spray. With the optimal condition, 250 - 300 Ω /cm² resistance with average of 93% transparency in the visible light wavelength was successfully gained (Fig. 2-4) (Table 1&2). Since, experiment goal was to achieve transparency higher than 93%, this value was set as optimal condition. During the preparation of SWCNT solution, it was noticed that large amount of surfactants were included in the SWCNT solution which helps SWCNT to disperse in the aqueous state. However, the surfactants act as somewhat insulator when it was sprayed on the PET film with SWCNT and free carrier movement was disturbed [4]. By treating SWCNT an isopropyl alcohol with distilled water, surfactant was removed as much as possible. 50% of Nitric acid was also applied to increase the conductivity of SWCNT by doping effect.

3.2. Polymerization of thiophene

Electropolymerization of thiophene occurs only at the anode side of electro cell [3]. If only one side of the substrate is applied to anodic current, the EDOT starts to polymerize from the anode side. This generates inhomogeneous formation of polythiophene on the substrate. To overcome this problem, specially designed stage was built to provide every side of substrate on anode. By controlling the reaction time and voltage applied, transparency was not affected at all (table 3). For test purpose, EDOT was fully polymerized for long period of time and all the voids between SWCNT networks filled by polythiophene were clearly observed (Fig. 5).

3.3. Effect of polymerization of thiophene on the SWCNT

EDOT is not soluble in water. It can be only dissolved by adding variety kinds of surfactant [5]. For doping effect and dissolving purpose, DBSA was used. In the experiment, it was noticed that the conductivity have close relationship with DBSA

concentration. Conductivity was high when the DBSA concentration was low. However, reaction did not happen if the concentration was too low or high. This can be due to the excess of dopant leaving accumulation of more surfactant on the SWCNT.

3.3 Conductivity enhancement of SWCNT theory

There are three factors that affect the conductivity of SWCNT film; Conductivity of SWCNT itself, concentration of SWCNT, and percolation threshold. All these factors are related to free carriers. Due to mechanical stiffness and physical properties, close and perfect contact between two SWCNT is really difficult to happen. This creates different kind of tunnel barriers. Some of the junctions can be electric conductive, free carriers can tunnel from one SWCNT in an adjacent SWCNT easily. Some other junctions are less electric conductive, free carriers have difficulty to cross over. Remaining junctions may be non conductive, which free carriers remain localized upon the SWCNT. These less electric conductive and non conductive junctions lower the conductivity of SWCNT. Improving the free carriers per unit area will allow the conductivity enhancement. SWCNT film has many voids between each SWCNT networks. These voids are somewhat decreasing the movement of free carriers to cross over.

4. Conclusion

SWCNT was sprayed on the PET film and PEDOT was applied to fill the void between CNT networks. This has allowed achieving high conductivity without sacrificing any transparency. In the future work, rolling and acid treatment could be done to increase conductivity more.

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Fig.1. SEM image of SWCNT sprayed on the PET film

Fig.2. Conductivity comparison graph between SWCNT and SWCNT-PEDOT

Fig.3. Conductivity graph of SWCNT film

Fig.4. Transparency graph of SWCNT

Fig.5. SEM image of SWCNT-PEDOT film

Table.3. Conductivity comparison between SWCNT film and SWCNT-PEDOT composite film

	CNT Resistance	CNT-PEDOT composite resistance
1 CNT Sprayed	4500 Ω/cm ²	2700Ω/cm ²
2 CNT Sprayed	2000Ω/cm ²	1500Ω/cm ²
3 CNT Sprayed	900Ω/cm ²	600Ω/cm ²
4 CNT Sprayed	350Ω/cm ²	250Ω/cm ²
5 CNT Sprayed	230Ω/cm ²	190Ω/cm ²

Tabel.1. Conductivity of SWCNT film

	CNT Resistance
1 CNT Sprayed	4500Ω/cm ²
2 CNT Sprayed	2000Ω/cm ²
3 CNT Sprayed	900Ω/cm ²
4 CNT Sprayed	350Ω/cm ²
5 CNT Sprayed	230Ω/cm ²

Table.2. Transparency of SWCNT film

	CNT Transparency
1 CNT Sprayed	98%
2 CNT Sprayed	97%
3 CNT Sprayed	95%
4 CNT Sprayed	93%
5 CNT Sprayed	89%